

Intelligent sorting system for recycling industrial, construction, demolition and packaging wastes

Applying artificial intelligence AI and robotics, identification and sorting of different types of wastes becomes more accurate, efficient, productive, reliable and economical viable, including wood-based wastes. In this specific case, the system provides both, “eyes and hands” with powerful sensors, smart trainable software and efficient heavy-duty robotic arms for municipal, private and industrial waste management operations. The system is designed for separation of wood by grade (A/B/C/D), metals, rigid plastics (mixed or polymer), inert mixed fractions and types of construction, demolition, industrial and packaging materials (bricks, concrete, stones, paperboard, etc.).

Regional coverage and transferability

The innovation and technology was developed in Finland for the needs of municipal and private waste collection and management centres at local and regional levels. The company, founded in 2007, is the first to apply AI-based sorting robots to a complex waste sorting environment. The system is currently in operational use on four continents globally already, therefore the technology can be further transferred to improve the value chains performances across Europe.

Image: ZenRobotics Ltd.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Increase accuracy, efficiency and economic viability of waste sorting, which makes recycling more profitable
- ▶ Decrease the need of pre-sorting wastes at construction, demolition, industrial and commercial sites
- ▶ Simple and energy efficient process with low operating costs
- ▶ Increase in the yield and allocation potential of cascading materials, instead of incineration or landfilling
- ▶ Advanced, unbiased detection and separation of hazardous materials with environmental or health risks
- ▶ Replacing manual processes and improving occupational safety
- ▶ System can be tailored to waste collection and management centres of different sizes and volumes
- ▶ Self-learning and trainable software technology provides continuous development to separate different material fractions and expand the recyclable material palette